

The Importance of Cryptography in Digital Signatures

Author Details: Dr. Yakubu Ajiji Maker

Kampala International University Uganda-School of Computing and Information Technology

Abstract

Information is an organization's most valuable asset. As we have seen in previous security and risk management is data-centric. The efforts to protect systems and networks attempt to achieve, data availability, confidentiality, Integrity, and the IP address of the devices that signed, we also saw no infrastructure security controls are not 100% effective. In reaction layered security model, it often necessary to underlying implement one final prevention control wrapped around sensitive information, Encryption is not a security panacea not solve all your data-centric security issues. This paper aim is to provide an extensive review of network security and to use cryptography is regard to digital signatures. Network security and cryptography is a subject to wide-ranging to coverage about how to protect the significant amount of information in digital form and to provide security services. In a general overview of network security and cryptography is provided, and various algorithms are discussed. The detailed of the subject of network security and cryptography in digital signatures are then presented. The purpose of a digital signature is to provide a means for an entity to bind its identity to a piece of information. The frequent attacks on digital signature were reviewed. The first method was the signature scheme, which remains today one of the most practical and versatile techniques available. The Fiat-Shamir signature schemes, DSA, and related signature schemes are two other methods reviewed a significant amount. The difference between an e-signature and digital signature are reasonably clear with the Digital signatures have many applications in information security, including authentication, data integrity, and non-repudiation was considered.

Whenever the advent of the e-commerce and the emergence of applications and World Wide Web and social networks across the world generate a large amount of data daily. And Data security is the utmost critical issue in ensuring secure, The IoT (Internet of Things) is not everywhere present transmission of information through the internet. Also, network security issues are now becoming famous as society is moving towards the digital information age. More users connect to the internet; it attracts a lot of cyber-criminals, and It comprises authorization of access to information in a network, controlled by the network administrator. The task of network security not only requires ensuring the safety of systems of the news or. In this paper, an attempt to review the various Network Security, and Cryptographic concepts and the broad range of cryptographic algorithms that are being used in networking applications.

Introduction

The essence of information security is to protect the information; It is just that simple. So whenever possible, do not make it more complicated than needed. Complexity for cybersecurity and The privacy arise when data needs to be shared or must be made accessible by most the digital device in every organization. The world where information is only available in physical archives is long gone, and the focus of physical information security is shifted to cyber information security configuring capabilities. But be aware, the Crucial principles of centuries of physical information protection are still valuable today. Especially policies related to the intangible soft issues when information is shared. Information protection is needed against unauthorized access, disclosure, modification, and destruction of information.

That means several measures are needed to protect information security from unauthorized user. Rules can be implemented by procedural, physical, or sophisticated IT tools. But before classifying and creating or finding

August 31, 2019

proper means, it is essential that the problem field is made clear. Creating practical solutions for information security problems can be done by creating a model of the problem situation. An algorithm works as an encrypted code to produce data that match the “hash.” Within a model everywhere, all elements that relate to the problem situation are brought together to study effective solutions the intended. Without going into detail on the system science or problem-solving, theory: in general systems consist of sub-systems, functions or processes, objects, and activities or tasks.

The Cryptography is the art and science of protecting information and an excellent model to solve a specific information security problem, with the complete system network security elements. This is because shaping the world entirely is ineffective, time-consuming it does not give a direct answer to solve a problem situation. Thus, it is now imperative, to start with a small model of a problem and create extensions on the field of modeling problem situations to solve information security Connectivity among systems. Many models Among in the literature exist Reusing a good model can save you time and safeguard from mistakes. The prerequisite is that you start with a good model that can be trusted and is intensively reviewed by large numbers of experts. Many good models on security can assist in creating a solution architecture to solve a specific security problem for many organizations.

Common attack vectors

Good security is goal oriented is a Good security architecture to tailored to your situation. When defining a product or new (IT) service, one of the key activities is to determine your specific security requirements. Defining requirements is known to be stressful, time-consuming, complicated. The Iterative development cycles and you do not have a clearly defined view of your final product or service to be created. Establishing attack vectors within your security network requirements documentation is proven to be helpful. With the Attack, vectors will give more focus on expected threats so you can start developing security measures that matter in your situation from the beginning. Many attacks, vectors take advantage of the human element on the system or one of the activities defined for each system because that’s often described as the weakest link remote systems on the network.

Vectors Common attack is:

- The Analysis of vulnerabilities in compiled software without source code
- Anti-forensic techniques
- Automated probes and scans
- Automated widespread attacks
- Client validation in AJAX routines
- Cross-site scripting in AJAX
- Cryptographic Performance Attacks
- Cyber-threats & bullying (not illegal in all jurisdictions)
- DoS Attacks
- Email propagation of malicious code
- Executable code attacks (against browsers)
- Exploiting Vulnerabilities

The earliest recommended that you specify in your solution architecture the attack vectors that apply to your networks, remember to put an explanation of the attack vectors used in an appendix, since not all your stakeholders will know that, e.g. ‘Spoofing.’

Privacy Management Reference Model

The Privacy Management Reference Model and Methodology (PMRM) of the OASIS group provides a model, and a methodology is:

- The Understanding and analyzing privacy policies and their privacy management requirements in defined use case
- The Selecting technical services obtained which must be implemented to support privacy controls on the network.

This model relevant to evaluate use cases in which personal information (PI) flows across the jurisdictional, policy, and system boundaries.

Source: OASIS - <http://docs.oasis-open.org/pmrm/PMRM/v1.0/csd01/PMRM-v1.0-csd01.html>

Cryptography

Cryptography is a science that applies complex mathematics and logic to design secure encryption methods on system security or network. Achieving the secure encryption, the hiding of data's meaning also requires intuitive leaps that allow the creative application of known or new techniques. So cryptography is also an art.

August 31, 2019

Types of Cryptography

The three common types of cryptographic functions which are used to encrypt and decrypt information

(a). Secret Key Cryptography – *secret-key cryptography* or asymmetric cryptography a sequence of bits, called the *secret key*, is used as an input to a mathematical function to encrypt a plaintext message; the same key is both used to decrypt the resulting ciphertext message and obtain the original plaintext. In this method of cryptography is useful if the numbers of communicating parties are limited. As the same key is used to both encrypt and decrypt data, a secret key is also called *asymmetric key*.

(b). Public key cryptography - Also known as asymmetric encryption uses more than one key for encryption and another set of keys for decryption. The two sets of keys work in synch with each other with the combination of public and private keys. Public keys can be shared between the sender and the receiver of the data. If they want to limit the access of data and maintain confidentiality, then they can only distribute the private keys. The RSA digital signature algorithm is used for the distribution and operation of the public keys.

(c). Hash Functions - Hash functions are used to mathematically transform the information permanently to protect it from illegal surveillance in the network. This encryption is known as one-way encryption or message-digesting request service from a system; the Hash functions employ a form of encrypted digital signature to information and is most often used by operating systems to protect data or data and measure the integrity of files. The RIPEMD and other types of secure hash functions are used for encrypting the data.

The Internet has become more and more widespread if an unauthorized person to gets accesses to this network, and spy on the system, but he can easily mess up our lives it by a cryptographic process and transmits it as *ciphertext*. Network Security and Cryptography is a concept to protect the network and data transmission over a network. A network security system typically relies on layers of protection and consists of multiple components, including networking monitoring and security software in addition to hardware and appliances. All parts work together to increase the security of the network and computer. Security of data can be done a technique called by(*cryptanalysis*) **cryptography**. So, cryptography is an emerging technology, which is essential for network security.

August 31, 2019

Network security covers a variety of computer networks, both public and private network that is used in every day conducting jobs transactions and communications among businesses, government agencies, and individuals on systems. Systems can be a company, such as within a private, and can be open to public access. Network security is involved in enterprises, organizations, and other institutions. It does as it explains: It secures the network, as well as protecting and overseeing operations being done. The most common and straightforward way of protecting a network resource is by assigning it a unique name and a corresponding password.

Monoalphabetic Substitution Ciphers method

One of the encryption methods is the shift cipher. With cipher is a process, or algorithm, that converts plaintext to ciphertext. Caesar’s shift cipher is known as a monoalphabetic substitution shift cipher. See Figure 1.

a	b	c	d	e	f	g	h	i	j	k	l	m	n	o	p	q	r	s	t	u	v	w	x	y	z	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	
7	8	9	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N	O	P	Q	R	S	T	U	V	W	X	Y	Z	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	Cipher Alphabet
t	h	e		t	a	n	k	s		w	i	l	l		a	r	r	i	v	e		a	t		1	3	0	0	Plain Text Message							
t	h	e		t	a	n	k	s		w	i	l	l		a	r	r	i	v	e		a	t	1	3	0	0									
Q	E	B	Q	7	K	H	P	T	F	I	I	7	O	O	F	S	B	7	Q	Y	0	X	X	Cipher Text Message												

Figure 7- 1: Monoalphabetic Substitution Shift Cipher

Types of Security Attacks

2.1. Passive Attacks

This type of attacks includes observation or monitoring of communication. A passive attack attempts to learn or make use of information from the system but does not affect system resources. The goal of the opponent is to obtain information that is being transmitted. Types of passive attacks:

- **Traffic Analysis:** The message traffic is sent and received data, and neither the sender or receiver is aware that he has read the messages or In the classical use of cryptography to protect communications observed the traffic pattern.
- **Release of Message Contents:** Read contents of the message from sender to receiver.

Active Attacks

An active attack attempts to alter system resources or affect their operation. It involves some modification of the data stream or the creation of a false stream. Types of active attacks:

- The **Change of Messages:** some portion of the legitimate message is altered, or that messages are delayed or reordered.
- The **Denial of Service:** An entity may suppress all messages directed to a particular destination.
- **Replay:** It involves the passive capture of a data unit and its subsequent retransmission to produce an unauthorized effect.

Security Services

It is a service that is provided by a protocol layer of communicating open systems, and that ensures adequate security of the order or data transfers. It enhances the security of data processing and transmission.

3.1. Integrity of Data

In the broad sense, Data integrity refers to the accuracy and consistency (validity) measures of data over its lifecycle. The Compromised data, after all, is of little use to enterprises, to mention the dangers presented by sensitive data loss apply to validation the stream of messages, a single word a loss of alterations and unauthorized modification or destruction of information.

3.2. Data Confidentiality

Preserving authorized restrictions on information access and disclosure, including means for protecting personal privacy and proprietary information. A loss of confidentiality is the unauthorized disclosure of information.

3.3. Authenticity

Provide authentication to all the node and base station for utilizing the limited available resources. It also ensures that only the authorized node can participant for the communication.

3.4. Nonrepudiation

Nonrepudiation prevents either sender or receiver from denying a transmitted message. Thus, when a message is sent, the receiver can prove that the alleged sender sent the message. Similarly, when a message is received, the sender can confirm the alleged receiver and has shown, obtained of the message.

3.5. Access Control

Access control is the ability to limit and control the access to host systems and applications via communications links. To achieve this, each entity trying to gain access must first be identified or authenticated, so that access rights can be tailored to the individual.

4. Network Security Model

Figure 3.4 – Model for Network Security

Methods of network attacks:

August 31, 2019

This section makes you aware of various threats targeting the security of your network and describes specific attacks that could be launched against a network.

As networks grow and interconnect with other systems, including the Internet, and those networks are exposed to a more significant number of security risks and not only does the number of potential attackers grow along with the interface with the size, but the tools available to those inherent

Network Security Principles

This chapter begins by broadly describing the necessity of network security and what should be in place in a secure network. Legal ramifications are addressed. Also, this chapter walks you through several specific types of attacks that could threaten your network. Finally, you are provided with a list of best-practice recommendations for mitigating such attacks.

5. Mechanism of Cryptography

The function of Cryptography is a method of storing and transmitting data in a particular form so that only those for whom is intended can read and process it. The term is most often associated with scrambling plaintext message (standard text, sometimes referred to as cleartext) into ciphertext (a process called **encryption**), then back again (known as **decryption**). There are, in general, three types of cryptographic schemes typically used to accomplish these goals: secret key (or symmetric) cryptography, public-key (or asymmetric) cryptography, and hash functions, each of which is described below.

5.1. Secret Key in Cryptography

With the secret key cryptography, a single key is used for both encryption and decryption as shown, the sender A uses the essential K (or some set of rules) to encrypt the plaintext message M and sends the ciphertext C to the receiver. The receiver applies the **same key** K (or ruleset) to decrypt the ciphertext C and recover the plaintext message M . Because the single key is used for both functions, secret key cryptography is also called **symmetric encryption** and With this form of cryptography, it is evident that the key must be known to both the sender and at the receiver another end; that is the secret. The most significant difficulty with this approach, of course, is the distribution of the key.

a). Digital Signature Without Hash Function

The digital signature standard (DSS) is a NIST standard that uses the secure hash algorithm (SHA). The digital signature is an authentication mechanism that enables the creator of a message to attach a code that acts as a signature. With this Typically the name is formed by taking the hash of the word and encrypting the message with the creator's private key. The signature guaranteed the source and integrity of the letter sent and received. The Figure shows the process of making and using digital signatures. The sender can sign a message using a digital signature generation algorithm. With the inputs to the algorithm are the message and the sender's private key. Any other user said receiver, and verify the signature using a verification algorithm, whose data are the message, signature, and sender's public key for both.

High level, of the RSA model, uses prime numbers to create a public and private key set:

1. The creation begins by selecting two huge prime numbers. They should be chosen at random and of similar length.
2. The two prime numbers are multiplied together.
3. The product becomes the public key.
4. The two factors become the private key.

Protecting the signature at the point of signing

A digital signature is an encrypted file that travels with the electronic document that needs to be signed and returns with it after the transaction has been completed. The archive contains and captures metadata about where the electronic record traveled which accounts opened it. Protection Profile about secure signature creation device with crucial generation and trusted communication with signature creation application (PP SSCD KG TCSCA) includes the security requirements for SSCD with key generation generating signature creation data (SCD) and creating digital signature to be used for (qualified or advanced) electronic signatures as

August 31, 2019

described in the core PP . With a pen and ink signature, you have handwriting identification as a base identification point. You can also have all parties signing a joint document present to view the procedure. For these essential documents, you can bring in a notary and collect identification for all parties involved. These features protect a physical signature. Similarly, a digital signature that captures the device that an electronic document is signed on, or records the user credentials of the person signing the form and captures the pathway that, the data traveled between destinations provides multiple tiers of signature verification, protecting the signing process in entirety.

2. Protecting signature in the storage devices

The electronic record needs to be stored for a significant amount of time, with the duration varying based on specific industry laws. It is often crucial to be able to verify that the signature has not been changed over time. A digital signature that is attached to the **electronic signature** features underlying technology that will show whether the form has been tampered with. It is, essentially, a digital watermark on the e-signature that verifies that the transaction has been completed and seals the file. Anything that breaks that seal is recorded in the digital signature, making it extremely difficult to tamper with the electronic file.

3. Protecting the signature on mobile devices

Smartphones and tablets are becoming pervasive technological tools, and as far as convenience is concerned, they are perfect for e-signing. However, they do not feature the security and data protection features needed to provide the same level of user authenticity as traditional PCs. A digital signature works around this problem by collecting critical metadata in a customizable format. If you need a digital signature to gather more user authentication data to verify a person using a smartphone, it can be configured to perform that task. The result is an operational climate in which you can safely have users sign electronic forms on a mobile device without creating any risk.

The differences between e-signature and digital signature are apparent, However, it is still plenty of confusion because the terms are often used interchangeably, to help solve this problem, we've created ,The electronic signing process as a whole will Check it out to get some clear insight on the terminology and functionality that defines the e-signature sector.

Digital signature Benefits

The **Digital signatures** are based on public-key **cryptography**, also known as asymmetric **cryptography**, Digital signatures are the public-key primitives of message authentication. Digital signatures as a specific subset. They are used to bind signatory to the message, a digital signature is a technique that links a person/entity to the digital data, and this binding can be independently verified by the receiver as well as any third party at the end.

Strengthen of security

When it comes to keeping confidential information secure, an electronic signature is one of the most important things you can have. In the online age, there are countless hackers and malicious schemes that exist solely to steal your data and, while they're at it, maybe your identity as well. With a digital signature, however, you can sign documents online without having to worry. Digital encryption and audit trails keep your name secure, protecting your organization against fraud and keeping your information away from prying eyes and hands that could do untold harm to a business if given the opportunity.

2. Cut Costs

Paper and printing can get expensive. Reducing paper waste has been known to save government organizations money in the past. For instance, according to the National Resources Defense Council, the EPA Region 10 offices in the Northwestern U.S. implemented paper-saving techniques that led to \$49,000 in annual savings. Maintaining a printer fleet is expensive – especially when clerks and admins are printing thousands of paper documents every day. With a digital signature, however, sending paper documents is unnecessary.

Not only will printing costs go down – so too will the expenses related to the actual procurement and processing of confidential files. According to the National Center for State Courts, electronic filing can reduce the costs associated with distributing paper files. Electronic filing with digital signatures, therefore, can save court and law organizations money. It also helps cut down on environmental waste, because you're not using snail mail to send documents.

3. High Level of Security

3DES

Triple Data Encryption Standard or 3DES, is a current standard, and it is a block cipher. It's similar to the older method of encryption, Data Encryption Standard, which uses 56-bit keys. While 3DES is symmetric-key encryption that uses three individual 56-bit keys. The Encrypts data three times, meaning your 56-bit key becomes a 168-bit key. This method is much slower than the others because 3DES uses shorter block lengths; it is easier to decrypt and leak data. There are already several theoretical and experimental approaches to cryptographic that promise security levels higher than anything we could have dreamed of.

Twofish

The Twofish is a symmetric block cipher based on an earlier block cipher – Blowfish. Twofish, submitted by a large team of researchers from Counterpane Internet Security, including noted cryptographer Bruce Schneier both and Twofish has a block size of 128-bits to 256 bits, and it works well on smaller CPUs and hardware, Similar to AES, it implements rounds of encryption to turn plaintext into ciphertext. However, the number of bullets doesn't vary as with AES; no matter the key size, there are always 16 rounds. Also, this method provides plenty of flexibility. You can choose for the critical set up to be slow but the encryption process to be quick or vice versa, Furthermore to implement, this form of encryption is unpatented and license-free so that you can use it without restrictions.

RSA

This asymmetric algorithm is named after Ron Rivest, Adi Shamir, and Len Adelman. It uses public-key cryptography to share data over an insecure network. There are two keys: one public and one private. The public key is just as the name suggests: public. Anyone can access it. However, the private key must be confidential. When using RSA cryptography, you need both keys to encrypt and decrypt a message. You use one key to encrypt your data and the other to decrypt it. According to Search Security, RSA is secure because it factors large integers that are the product of two large prime numbers.

Additionally, the critical size is large, which increases the security. The RSA or *Rivest-Shamir-Adleman* encryption algorithm is one of the most powerful forms of encryption in the world. It supports incredibly key lengths, and it is typical to see 2048- and 4096- bit keys, the more crucial extended size does mean it's slower

August 31, 2019

than other encryption methods. The, While there are many additional encryption methods available, knowing about and using the most secure ones ensures your confidential data stays safe and away from unwanted eyes.

Conclusion

The history of cryptography is filled with the back-and-forth between cryptographers creating “unbreakable” ciphers and cryptanalysts breaking the unbreakable. However, valuable lessons from the centuries-old battle are used to strengthen today’s ciphers. Mainly, any cipher creating ciphertext containing frequency and character/word socialization characteristics of the plaintext language is not secure. The more the ciphertext changes after a change to the plaintext, the stronger the cipher. The key management is an essential and often overlooked aspect of enterprise encryption. Ensuring keys are always available, secure, and locked away from everyone except a handful of critical administrators is a good start.

Further, important central management usually comes with the ability to apply standard encryption policies across all data on all managed devices. The battle cry, “ENCRYPT EVERYTHING!” is not a consistent and appropriate application of encryption as a security control system. To compliance or to decide when and where to encrypt based on risk assessments and management’s appetite for risk. Finally, considered it is sometimes a better solution than encryption for protecting individual data items. Credit card numbers, Social security numbers, and patient insurance information are good examples of possible token targets.

References

- i. ANSI X9.19, *Financial Institution Retail Message Authentication*, American Bankers Association, August 13, 1986.
- ii. ANSI X9.52, *Triple Data Encryption Algorithm Modes of Operation*, American Bankers Association, 1998.
- iii. E. Barkan, E. Biham, N. Keller, *Instant ciphertext-only cryptanalysis of GSM encrypted communication*, *Advances in Cryptology, Proceedings Crypto’03*, LNCS 2729, D. Boneh, Ed., Springer, Heidelberg, 2003, pp. 600–616.
- iv. M. Bellare, *New proofs for NMAC and HMAC: Security without collision-resistance*, *Advances in Cryptology, Proceedings Crypto’06*, LNCS 4117, C. Dwork, Ed., Springer, Heidelberg,

August 31, 2019

2006, pp. 602–619. Ed., Springer, Heidelberg, 1996, pp. 1–15.

- v. M. Bellare, R. Canetti, H. Krawczyk, Keying hash functions for message authentication, *Advances in Cryptology, Proceedings Crypto '96, LNCS 1109*, N. Kobnitz,
- vi. REFERENCES Adams, A., & Sasse, M. A. (1999). Users are not the enemy: why users compromise security mechanisms and how to take remedial measures. *Communications of the ACM*, 42 (12), 40-46.
- vii. Ajzen, I. (1991). The theory of planned behavior. *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes*, 50(2), 179-211.
- viii. Albrechtsen, E. (2007). A qualitative study of users' view on information security. *Computers & Security*, 26(4), 276-289.
- ix. Anderson, R. (2001). *Security engineering: a guide to building dependable distributed systems*. Wiley John Wiley & sons.
- x. Anderson, R., & Moore, T. (2007). *Information Security Economics-and Beyond*. *Advances in Cryptology -CRYPTO7*, 68-91.
- xi. Angelia, D. A., Coventrya, L., Johnsona, G., & Renaudb, K. (2005). Is a picture really worth a thousand words? Exploring the feasibility of graphical authentication systems. *International Journal of Human-Computer Studies*, 63(1), 128-152.
- xii. M. Bellare, C. Namprempre, Authenticated encryption: Relations among notions and analysis of the generic composition paradigm, *Advances in Cryptology, Pro- ceedings Asiacrypt '00, LNCS 1976*, T. Okamoto, Ed. (Springer, Heidelberg, 2000) 531–545.